

FORMS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT IN ADOLESCENTS.

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Darobov Rahmonjon Ravshanovich

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi, Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology, student of Pedagogy and Psychology, group 302

Annotation.

In this article, respecting the rights of the child means solving problems together, involving the child in family affairs (allowing them to participate in the decision), fully accepting the child's personality, but not necessarily accepting his behavior, in the adolescent period. Information about crises is given.

Keywords.

positive emotional response, gentle methods of education, explanation of commands and punishment

Coming of age is the process of the child becoming an adult, the gradual formation of certain abilities to meet the demands of adults, the future role of a parent, spouse, worker, member of society and life in general. All of them are expressed in the jump of individual functions from maturity to maturity.

In the field of intellectual functions: from reliance on authority in everything to the search for evidence; from attention to facts, specifics - to explanations and reasoning; from the variability and multiplicity of interests to their concentration and stability.

Formation of the emotional sphere: balance from imbalance, childhood fears and conflict avoidance, balance, adult motivation and the desire to resolve conflict situations.

In the field of social activity: from the fear of rejection, imitation, helplessness and uncertainty - the desire to feel a sense of self-acceptance, independence and social entrepreneurship.

In the area of independence from parents: the desire to control, rely on parents and independently control their behavior and feelings, to be self-reliant and to establish friendships with parents.

Formation of self-esteem: adequate perception of self-esteem, self-esteem, calm acceptance of other people's opinions and self-evaluation from unrealistic self-esteem and setting unrealistic goals caused by fear of social evaluation and

disapproval until done. , setting realistic goals and realistic planning. Emotional development of a teenager directly depends on the level of formation of intellectual maturity, ongoing hormonal and physical changes, as well as socio-cultural factors. Emotional development is characterized by: unusual intensity and vividness of emotions, emotions are often very difficult, small events can be experienced as "the end of the world", and in the face of objectively insignificant failures, there is a sense of meaninglessness of life; fast quick suicidal thoughts and even suicide for minor reasons; emotional instability, fluctuating feelings are characterized by easy and very quick jumps from extreme depression and sadness to euphoria, so it is important to ensure that the child is closely accompanied in all his experiences, it is important to orient his activities in this way. momentarily bad in the mood he does not do stupid things; it is also characterized by a feeling of little strength and power, a breakdown, psychological weakness, and easy throwing to lose confidence in one's little powers and abilities; the meaninglessness of emotions, the teenager often cannot determine why he is sad or happy, what caused him, etc.; the reason for this condition lies in strong hormonal changes that affect the work of the nervous system as mentioned above, social and cultural factors, especially family relations, have a great influence on the development and formation of a teenager. The most important thing in adolescence is the support provided by parents. In addition, family has a very broad meaning. The duties of the family include: meeting the needs of the child, who is still a teenager, who is gradually preparing for the role of spouse, parent, worker, etc.; to be a source of experience and knowledge about life

Forming personality, tastes, preferences, habits, providing the right examples (the child's copying of their parents, any of their behavior, methods of coping with problems and stress serves as a certain guide for him). If a teenager scares us with his behavior, excites us with his words, statements, way of thinking, we should think about whether we ourselves have given him a reason to think like that and whether we are a bad example (child abuse) with our small actions (to yourself see); providing a model of attitude to life, a worldview.

During adolescence, the strength of the family's influence on the child also changes. The crisis of the authority of parents and adults in general is coming. Conflicts with parents are becoming more frequent, intergenerational conflict occurs as a result of the teenager's criticality, observation of parents' mistakes, increased level of thinking, which leads to a weakening of the emotional connection with the teenager.

That is, intellectual ability and resourcefulness, the child's ability to observe and make a little independent assessment of everything, and therefore to be more critical of his parents' shortcomings, increase.

Adolescents come to the conclusion that they themselves do not follow the rules and principles announced by adults, which means that their theories are not reflected in practice. This leads to a general loss of trust in adults and, as mentioned above, a generational conflict at the same time, the situation of quarrels with parents, which took the form of a dominant background, the atmosphere prevailing in the house, in turn, leads to a weakening of the emotional connection with the family, an indifference to its problems.

Another consequence of adolescence is the recognition by parents that the child's behavior is a signal and confirmation that he does not need the strong support and love that he previously received. But it is impossible to imagine something different from the truth - in the context of satisfying psycho-emotional needs, a teenager should be treated like a small child, although, of course, it is very difficult, because of his arrogance, conflict and often ingratitude. Perhaps the healthy distance of the adult from the age, expressed in a certain form through words and communication, helps to prevent his psycho-emotional alienation from his family. The reasons for the ongoing changes in family influence are: Inappropriate behavior of parents - failure to adapt to changes in the child's development, his changing needs; along with the development of the child, there must be changes in the methods of raising children, because the old ones cease to be effective and only those of the parents accelerate the decline of their reputation, they often try to preserve it with the help of prohibitions, instructions, threats, , punishments, and in the end they achieve only one result - the teenager just breaks family ties. Only following the child is an effective way to maintain proper family relations with him during adolescence;

Gradual maturation of young people, initially external - physical changes, imitation of other people's behavior, style of clothing, etc.; expansion of social relations, a sense of high readiness for new achievements and a good direction in the surrounding world. Independence, the need to have sole control over one's life and actions, and therefore to free oneself from the parental wing, the need to do something on one's own (at the same time, teenagers are not so optimistic about taking responsibility). their actions and decisions for);

We have analyzed the theory and scientific data by studying the development of youth periods in the science of developmental psychology, the stages of

periodization and their problems, and psychological crises related to age, and our conclusion on this topic is as follows

Developmental psychology Originally associated with infants and children, this field has expanded to include adolescence, adult development, aging, and the entire lifespan. Developmental psychologists explain how thinking, feeling, and behavior change throughout life this domain examines changes in three key dimensions: physical development, cognitive development, and social-emotional development. Within these three dimensions are broad themes such as motor skills, executive functions, moral understanding, language acquisition, social change, personality, emotional development, self-awareness, and identity formation.

We learned that developmental psychology examines the influence of nature and nurture on the process of human development, as well as the processes of context change over time. Many researchers were interested in the interaction between personal characteristics, individual behavior and environmental factors, and we considered the historical-scientific significance of related theories. This includes the social context and the built environment.

Change is inevitable. As humans, we are constantly hanging around throughout our lives, from pregnancy to adulthood. Psychologists seek to understand and explain how and why people change throughout life. While most of these changes are normal and expected, they can still cause problems that people need extra help to manage.

Normative development principles help professionals identify potential problems and provide early intervention for better outcomes. Developmental psychologists can work with people of all ages to overcome barriers and support coping, although some choose to specialize in a specific age group, such as childhood, adulthood, or old age.

A psychologist or other highly trained professional may administer a developmental screening or assessment to determine whether a developmental problem exists. For children, such evaluations usually involve interviewing parents and other caregivers to learn about their observed behaviors, reviewing the child's medical history, and taking standardized tests to measure communication, social/emotional skills, and physical/motor skills includes

If a problem is identified, the patient may then be referred to a specialist such as a speech pathologist, physiotherapist or occupational therapist. Getting diagnosed with a developmental problem can often be confusing and scary, especially when your child is affected after you or a loved one has been diagnosed

with a developmental problem, learn as much as you can about the diagnosis and available treatments.

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